

CHEMOTHERAPEUTIC AGENT : A NOTE (A special Pandemic Issue)

By

Datta et al (Jaydip Datta , Dimitri Ketchakmadze & Muhammad Akram)

Neoplasm, Tumour, Malignant, Oncogene, Cancer, Chemotherapy, SAR, Pandemic ,Covid19

As we know that the word neoplasm means a Tumor. A Malignant Tumor is known as Cancer – ONCO-GENE activation or abnormal growth of tumor. The stoppage of this genetic signal /onco- gene activation is a great challenge of twentieth century!

N.B - The Patients suffering with Cancer have a great chance of pneumonic attack followed by death due to attack of SARS-COV-2. So they are advised to take balanced food with highly anti-oxidant course to increase the immunity.

In this note we will point out **Anti-Cancer Drugs or Chemo-therapeutic agent or Anti-neoclassic agents** mainly very few synthetic Medicine , Chelating Complex and some alkaloids from phyto – chemicals . The basic theory or from structure activity relationship (SAR) to de-accelerate the growth of the tumour is to bind the DNA of ONCO-GENE . The Chemotherapeutic agents named as follows.

Antibiotics from synthetic origin is a Chemical Compound so accordingly the therapy should be known as **CHEMOTHERAPY** . But this type of treatment is specifically used for treating cancers .

.

. From classical concept that any **antibiotic** (From Penicillin to Ciprofloxacin) used in common diseases was termed as Chemotherapy . But modern medical management the term CHEMO . is used to treat all types of CANCERS.CIS -PLATIN ,CARBOPLATIN , PACLITAXEL are used as CHEMOTHERAPEUTIC AGENT FOR ANTICANCER MEDICINE in India .

METHOTREXATE, MELPHALAN all are classical chemotherapeutic agents.

METHOTREXATE can also be used in the treatment of Rheumatoid Arthritis.

Some alkaloids from phyto-Chemical origin are **VINCA alkaloid** like vinblastine, vincristine.

REFERENCE –

1. [https://www.researchgate.net/post/Whether any antibiotic therapy of any diseases can be termed as CHEMOTHERAPY2](https://www.researchgate.net/post/Whether_any_antibiotic_therapy_of_any_diseases_can_be_terminated_as_CHEMOTHERAPY2) - JAYDIP DATTA
2. [https://www.researchgate.net/post/Development of Antineoplastics-A mini review](https://www.researchgate.net/post/Development_of_Antineoplastics-A_mini_review) - JAYDIP DATTA
3. <https://medlineplus.gov/druginfo/meds/a682019.html>
4. <https://medlineplus.gov/druginfo/meds/a682220.html#:~:text=Melphalan%20is%20used%20to%20treat,of%20medications%20called%20alkylating%20agents.>
5. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4146684/>
6. <https://go.drugbank.com/drugs/DB00958>
7. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378517301009863#:~:text=Paclitaxel%20dosage%20form,years%20at%204%20%C2%B0C.>
8. <https://chemoth.com/types/vinca-alkaloids>
10. JAYDIP DATTA , COVID 19 – An Environmental Spasmodemic ! ,March 2020 ,DOI: [10.6084/m9.figshare.13456403](https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.13456403) ,License [CC BY-ND 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nd/4.0/) ([https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340163679_COVID_19 - An Environmental Spasmodemic? _sg=SHRBvhHin75_hnXq5y8K5SzStJcGxAPhjJAfnQE_HKz0QgOxvZnHbwQiEJZ8dhoOfAAbrSu69-JI1tOEbsFeLUpEHwXPhl_WAR0cwzJR.xZg9UiRC629ur5LHGILqKKF1LhKEK_s2VafxKRE_VyNfR6TsantfPq3tXvWVNPMCqRvnP-nREKhefxhtagX4s8Q](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340163679_COVID_19_-_An_Environmental_Spasmodemic?_sg=SHRBvhHin75_hnXq5y8K5SzStJcGxAPhjJAfnQE_HKz0QgOxvZnHbwQiEJZ8dhoOfAAbrSu69-JI1tOEbsFeLUpEHwXPhl_WAR0cwzJR.xZg9UiRC629ur5LHGILqKKF1LhKEK_s2VafxKRE_VyNfR6TsantfPq3tXvWVNPMCqRvnP-nREKhefxhtagX4s8Q)) .
11. JAYDIP DATTA , A Photo Sensitized CHEMOTHERAPEUTIC modeled complex .September 2008 ,DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.2.26850.25288/2](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26850.25288/2) ([https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335222923_A_Photo_Sensitized_CHEMOTHERAPEUTIC_modeled_complex? _sg%5B0%5D=55hTaoURCsfahJTFN2HC8unn6FazGKzsYH68k4tRgs9l0ayZn5kRLo6HY1KWypOs1IjCivgLmQZeBCVazeAXK6HsxUccLwJkYHMFJp-M.aayAEBe-1vdKI35kv19dV0nM3UL8sUQpLEvHc0sCbo7S68cm1gcc9ok3LZYcBIjfc9_4gEaLSYU52ucBnAyW_w](https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335222923_A_Photo_Sensitized_CHEMOTHERAPEUTIC_modeled_complex?_sg%5B0%5D=55hTaoURCsfahJTFN2HC8unn6FazGKzsYH68k4tRgs9l0ayZn5kRLo6HY1KWypOs1IjCivgLmQZeBCVazeAXK6HsxUccLwJkYHMFJp-M.aayAEBe-1vdKI35kv19dV0nM3UL8sUQpLEvHc0sCbo7S68cm1gcc9ok3LZYcBIjfc9_4gEaLSYU52ucBnAyW_w))